

Histopathological Spectrum of Thyroid Lesions at A Tertiary Care Center in Western Rajasthan

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Abstract:

Background: Thyroid disorders are the second most prevalent endocrine conditions worldwide, with India facing a significant burden. This retrospective study investigates the histopathological spectrum of thyroid lesions at a tertiary care center in Western Rajasthan over one year.

Results: The study involved 37 patients, aged between 10 to 86 years, with a mean age of 40.16 years. Females were predominantly affected, accounting for 94.6% of cases, with a male-to-female ratio of 17.5:1. Histopathological analysis revealed that 59.4% of the lesions were non-neoplastic, while 40.5% were neoplastic. Among non-neoplastic lesions, multinodular goiter (27.0%) was the most common, followed by adenomatous goiter (13.5%). Neoplastic lesions were primarily benign (27.0%), with follicular adenoma being the most frequent (13.5%). Malignant lesions constituted 13.5% of the total cases, with papillary carcinoma being the most common (5.4%).

Conclusion: In conclusion, this study underscores the importance of periodic evaluation of thyroid swellings, particularly in middle-aged women, to detect potential carcinomatous changes early. The high incidence of neoplastic lesions at this tertiary center suggests the need for enhanced diagnostic protocols and awareness programs, particularly in iodine-deficient regions.

Keywords: Thyroid, Papillary Carcinoma, Goiter, Histopathology.

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Introduction

Thyroid gland is one of the important endocrine glands in our body. It is located in along the 2nd, 3rd, and 4th tracheal rings in front of the trachea and weighs around 20–25 gm. [1]

Thyroid gland lesions are the most common endocrine disorders encountered globally second only to diabetes mellitus. In India too, there is a significant burden of thyroid diseases. It has been estimated that about 42 million people in India suffer from thyroid diseases. [2] Thyroid swellings are frequent and occur in population aged between 30 and 60 years. [3] However, the thyroid gland lesions vary in their incidence and histopathological patterns depending upon factors like geographic location, age, sex, diet, and environmental conditions.

The thyroid gland is affected by a wide range of conditions, extending from functional and immunologically mediated enlargements to malignant tumors. [4] Clinically detectable thyroid nodules are found in about 4–5% of the population. [5] The etiology of thyroid disorders is complex

and multifactorial, involving various contributing factors like Iodine deficiency, radiation exposure, hormonal imbalances, genetic predispositions, dietary factors, and exposure to goitrogens are all recognized as potential contributors to thyroid disease pathogenesis. Iodine deficiency still remains the most common factor associated with thyroid lesions worldwide contributing around one third of the total cases of thyroid lesions. [6,7]

In iodine-sufficient areas, autoimmune thyroid disease is a more frequent cause of goiter than iodine deficiency. Out of all the thyroid malignancies, papillary carcinoma of the thyroid is the most prevalent, followed by follicular, medullary, and anaplastic carcinomas. These neoplastic conditions may be associated with either hyperthyroidism or hypothyroidism, depending on the underlying pathology. [8]

Various diagnostic modalities are available for thyroid lesions starting from thyroid hormone levels in blood, TSH levels, and radiological investigation like ultrasonography and radio

isotope assays. FNAC is a commonly used technique for the initial detection of thyroid nodules and is considered to be the best primary diagnostic procedure. [9] Thyroid carcinoma often closely resembles benign thyroid nodules in terms of physical appearance, measurable serum levels of T3 and T4, and even ultrasound characteristics many a times. Due to this similarity, distinguishing between benign and malignant nodules can be challenging through non-invasive methods alone. Therefore, surgical excision biopsy and histological examination remains the gold standard method for differentiating the more common benign nodules from the less frequent malignant ones so that further management of the lesion can be planned. [10]

The present study was conducted to determine the histopathological spectrum of thyroid lesions at a tertiary care center in western Rajasthan.

Materials and Methods

This is a retrospective study conducted over a period of one year from June 2023 to April 2024 at the Department of Pathology, at a tertiary care teaching hospital, SPMC and associated group of hospitals, Bikaner. The biopsies of thyroid lesions received from ENT department and Surgery department at the Department of Pathology during the study period were included in our study as per the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Specimens with improper clinical records, Autolyzed specimens or specimens received without fixative, patients with benign and inflammatory lesions and patients who refused to give consent were excluded from the study.

The clinical and relevant data were recorded from requisition form and clinical records. The specimens received were fixed in 10% buffered formalin. Gross examination was done, and findings recorded. The tissues were sectioned as per protocol and processed by wax block method. Slides were stained with hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) stain and examined under light microscope. Various histopathological spectrum of lesions in the thyroid were observed and classified as benign

and malignant on the basis of World Health Organization histological classification of the thyroid tumors.

Statistical analysis was done using Microsoft Excel 2019. Data was collected and entered into excel. The analysis was done by calculating ratios, proportion, and percentage.

Results

In the present study, we studied a total of 37 patients with thyroid swellings. Patient's age ranged from 10 years and 86 years with the mean age of 40.16 years with standard deviation of 17.02 years. The most common age group affected was 30-39 years with 10 (27.03%) cases (Table -1). We observed a major female predominance in our study. Out of total 37 cases; 35 cases (94.6%) were females, and only 2 cases (5.4%) were male with male to female ratio of 17.5: 1. On classifying the lesions, out of total 37 cases, non-neoplastic lesions were most common with 22 cases (59.4%) [Table-2], whereas in 15 (40.5%) neoplastic lesions, benign neoplastic lesions were more common with 10 cases (27%) and malignant neoplastic lesions were 5 cases (13.5%). [Table-2] Most common non-neoplastic lesion was multinodular goiter, with 10 cases (27.02%), followed by adenomatous goitre with 5 (13.5%) cases. The most common benign neoplastic lesion was follicular adenoma with 5 cases (13.51%) and most common malignant neoplastic lesion was papillary carcinoma with 2 cases (5.4%).

In our study out of 22 cases (59.4%) of non-neoplastic lesions 20 cases (54%) were seen in females and 2 (5.4%) cases were seen in males. All 10 cases (27%) of neoplastic benign lesions and 5 cases (13.5%) of neoplastic malignant lesions were seen in females. On studying the distribution of non-neoplastic, benign and malignant cases between different age groups we did not find any significant statistical difference which shows that different types of lesions occurred similar in different ages in our study (p-value = 0.295). [Table 3]

Figure 1: Box plot showing the age statistics in the present study

Table 1: Age and sex distribution of cases in the present study

Age Groups	Female		Male		Total	
	Count	%	Count	%	Count	%
10 - 19	1	50.0%	1	50.0%	2	5.41%
20 - 29	8	100.0%	0	0.0%	8	21.62%
30 - 39	10	100.0%	0	0.0%	10	27.03%
40 - 49	5	83.3%	1	16.7%	6	16.22%
50 - 59	5	100.0%	0	0.0%	5	13.51%
60 - 69	5	100.0%	0	0.0%	5	13.51%
70 - 79	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.00%
80+	1	100.0%	0	0.0%	1	2.70%
Total	35	94.6%	2	5.4%	37	100.00%

Figure 2: Distribution of cases in different types of lesions

Table 2: Prevalence of different types of thyroid lesions in the present study.

Type of Lesion	Diagnosis	Count	%	Male	%	Female	%
Non-neoplastic	Adenomatous goiter	5	13.5%	1	2.7%	4	10.8%
	Colloid goiter	4	10.8%	0	0	4	10.8%
	Multinodular goiter	10	27.0%	0	0	10	27.0%
	Lymphocytic thyroiditis	2	5.4%	0	0	2	5.4%
	Thyroglossal cyst	1	2.7%	1	2.7%	0	0
	Total	22	59.4%	2	5.45	20	54%
Benign	Adenomatous hyperplasia	4	10.8%	0	0	4	10.8%
	Follicular Adenoma	5	13.5%	0	0	5	13.5%
	Hyalinizing trabecular adenoma	1	2.7%	0	0	1	2.7%
	Total	10	27%	0	0	10	27%
Malignant	Follicular variant - Papillary carcinoma	1	2.7%	0	0	1	2.7%
	Hashimoto's thyroiditis - papillary micro carcinoma	1	2.7%	0	0	1	2.7%
	Medullary thyroid carcinoma	1	2.7%	0	0	1	2.7%
	Papillary Carcinoma	2	5.4%	0	0	2	5.4%
	Total	5	13.5%	0	0	5	13.5%

Table 3: Distribution of different types of lesions between age groups.

Age Groups	Type of Lesion			Total
	Non-Neoplastic	Benign	Malignant	
10 - 19	1	1	0	2
20 - 29	7	1	0	8
30 - 39	4	4	2	10
40 - 49	5	1	0	6

50 - 59	3	1	1	5
60 - 69	2	2	1	5
70 - 79	0	0	0	0
80+	0	0	1	1
Total	22	10	5	37

Chi-square = 14.082; df = 12; p-value = 0.295 (NS)

Figure 3: (A) showing gross specimen of colloid goiter. The cut surface shows tan colored colloid material. (B) showing gross specimen of adenomatous goiter

Figure 4: Showing hyalinizing trabecular tumor of thyroid gland (10x, H&E)

Figure 5: Section showing follicular adenoma (40x, H&E)

A

B

Figure 6: (A) Gross specimen of Papillary carcinoma of thyroid gland. (B) showing the microscopic feature of same tumor (40x, H&E)

Discussion

The occurrence of thyroid diseases varies according to gender, age groups, and racial differences. Neoplastic and non-neoplastic thyroid diseases are common all over the world with varying frequency and incidence depending on iodine deficiency and other environmental factors. Thyroid lesions may be developmental, inflammatory, hyperplastic, and neoplastic. The thyroid gland diseases are common and composed of an array of entities causing

systemic disease (grave's disease) or a localized abnormality in the thyroid gland such as nodular enlargement (goiter) or a tumor mass.

In our present study, the age of the patients ranged from 10 years to 86 years with a mean age of 40.16 ± 17.02 years which was similar with the study of Padmom L [11] and Nggada et al. [12] with a mean age of 37 years and 40.7 years respectively. Maximum number of lesions were seen in patients in the age group of 30-39 years (n=37, 29%) which

was were lower when compared with study conducted by Padmom L [11] with maximum number of lesions in patients in the age group of 41-50 years (n=139, 29%) and Nggada et al. [12] between 20 and 40 years of age. The results signify that thyroid lesions are most manifested in middle age groups with minor variations in different studies, which may depend on the geographical area, and food habits and iodine content in the soil and salt.

In the present study, we observed a drastic female predominance with 35 (94.6%) cases were females and 2 (5.4%) cases were male. The female to male ratio found in this study was 17.5:1. Most previous studies like the study by Padmom L [11] with M: F ratio 6:1, Nggada et al. [12] with ratio 6:1; Garalla and Gheryani [13] with ratio 8:1 reported female predominance; however, we observed quite a high ratio of female patients in our study. In women the high frequency of developing thyroid disorders is due to the physiological demands of puberty, menstruation, pregnancy, and lactation. Significantly higher proportion of female patients in our study can be attributed to a combination of biological, environmental, and sociocultural factors. Dietary patterns, such as the consumption of goitrogenic foods, and increased healthcare-seeking behavior for reproductive and thyroid-related symptoms, further contribute to this gender disparity in thyroid lesions. Mandatory thyroid screening program for all pregnant females in Rajasthan may also contribute to increasing number of female's patients of thyroid lesions.

Thyroid specimens were analyzed on morphological basis which showed non-neoplastic lesions 22 cases (59.45%), neoplastic benign lesions 10 cases (27.02%) and neoplastic malignant lesions 5 cases (13.51%). Neoplastic cases contributing to 15 cases (49.53%). These findings are comparable with the study done by Ijomone et al. [14] who reported 66.91% non-neoplastic and 31.57% neoplastic lesions. Authors like Padmom L[11] who reported non- neoplastic 419 cases (88.1%) and neoplastic lesions 57 cases (11.9%) and Turkey HA[15] which showed non-neoplastic lesions 67 cases (83.75%) and neoplastic lesions, 13 cases (16.25%) have comparatively less number of neoplastic cases as compared to our study. The higher number of neoplastic lesions at our center can be due to the fact that ours is a tertiary care cancer center and cancer patients from a wide geography visit our facility for treatment. The variation in the incidence rates of neoplastic and nonneoplastic thyroid lesions in different studies could also be due to geographical and racial factors.

Non neoplastic lesions: Adenomatous goiter constituted 5 cases (13.5%) of the cases studied. Age of the patients ranged from 22 to 40 years;

however, majority of the cases were seen in the age group of 20-29 years amounting to 80% of the cases. The lesion was seen predominantly in females as compared to males, where females accounted for 80% (4 cases) of the cases and males constituted 20% (1 case). Tsegaye and Ergete [16] also found female preponderance where 82% of the patients were females and 18% were males. Other non-neoplastic lesions were colloid goitre, lymphocytic thyroiditis and thyroglossal cyst with 4 cases (10.8%), 2 cases (5.4%) and 1 case (2.7%) respectively. Study conducted by Prabha V [19] showed concordant results with incidence 29%, 9% and 3% respectively.

In our study the most predominant thyroid lesion encountered is multinodular goiter and was commonly seen in the age group 30-39 years. It constituted 27% of all lesions. Multi nodular goiter (MNG) is the end-stage result of diffuse hyperplastic goiter. Excessive metabolic demands in this condition will lead to the increased enlargement of the thyroid gland and this is one of the important reasons for the thyroid enlargement in women during puberty and pregnancy which is considerably common. Constant stimulation by the TSH released from the anterior pituitary results in multi-nodular goiter (MNG). Main reason for colloid goiter is iodine deficiency. While in a study conducted by Sankaran V [17] and Arora and Gupta [18] the incidence of multinodular goiter was 18% and 3.19% respectively which is comparatively lower than our study.

Benign Neoplasms: Follicular Adenomas were present in 13.5% of all the cases studied. In our study, follicular adenomas were the second most common lesions encountered same as adenomatous goiter. All the cases studied were females. In the study conducted by Tsegaye and Ergete [16], adenomas were the second most common lesion encountered accounting for 12.8% of cases, preceded only by adenomatous goiter, the results are concordant with our study.

Hyalinizing trabecular adenoma was found in 1 case with 2.7% incidence. It is an uncommon thyroid tumor that is usually benign and is, often misdiagnosed as another thyroid neoplasm, such as papillary thyroid carcinoma or medullary thyroid carcinoma due to its similar nuclear features as PTC or the presence of hyaline material resembling amyloid in MTC.

Malignant Neoplasms: We discovered 1 case of follicular variant - Papillary carcinoma with (2.7%) incidence in our study. In a study conducted by Tsegaye and Ergete [16], it constituted for 15.6% of the malignant tumors (n=64). Urmiladevi P et al. [20] in their review published 3 (15%) cases of follicular variant of papillary carcinoma.

Hashimoto's thyroiditis papillary micro carcinoma was found in 1 case (2.7%). It is the most common form of malignancy associated with hashimoto's thyroiditis.

Papillary carcinoma was the most common malignant thyroid lesion and constituted 5.4% of the malignant lesions in our study. This observation was similar with the study of Tsegaye and Ergete [16] which also showed most common malignant lesion to be papillary carcinoma. Histopathologically papillary carcinoma appears as colloid-filled follicles with papillary projections along with psammoma bodies which may be present in calcified lesions. Old females are commonly affected in the age group of 60-80 years.

Medullary thyroid carcinoma incidence in our study was 1 case (2.7%) same as study by Turkey HA[15] which had 2 cases (2.5%).

Limitations: The limitation of the study is that it was carried out in a single tertiary care hospital in India; hence this may not represent the entire population of the nation. Similar studies with a larger sample size should be conducted in multiple centers which would provide a clearer picture of the thyroid lesions in India.

Conclusion

In our study, thyroid diseases showed definite female predominance, with most of them occurring in an age group of 30-39 years. MNG is the most common disease. Follicular adenoma was the most common benign neoplastic disease. Papillary carcinoma was most common malignant neoplastic lesion. This study emphasizes the need for periodic evaluation of middle-aged and young female patients with MNG for early detection of carcinomatous changes. Also this study highlights the importance of histomorphological typing of thyroid lesions for their better management.

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